

Prediction of physical parameters of F Type Stars by Neural Network algorithm.

Project Report

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by

**Avirup Chakraborty
Junior Research Fellow**

**under the supervision of
Prof. Soumen Mondal**

**Dept. of Astrophysics and High Energy Physics
S.N. Bose National Centre for Basic Sciences
Kolkata**

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1. Introduction

Determination of the stellar parameters of a star is of paramount importance in understanding the physics going deep inside the stellar atmosphere. The task is undoubtedly challenging because of several factors. One of which is that stars are very distant, therefore their radiation suffers severe absorption by the interstellar dust and gas medium as well as atmospheric noises itself present in our earth. This makes the job of determining the stellar parameters accurately, a field of research on its own merit. Since the beginning of the study of astrophysics, when the first spectrograph was made, several strides has been taken in the direction of stellar spectroscopy and hence our knowledge of stellar atmospheres have grown to a broader extent.

The late 20th century has marked a significant evolution in computational stellar spectroscopy, driven by advances in computational power, numerical methods, and the development of sophisticated models of stellar atmospheres. Research in this field has focused on improving the precision of spectral analysis, developing detailed models for various types of stars, and applying these models to understand stellar structure, evolution, and chemical composition. In the late 20th century, the field began to focus on the development of 1D stellar atmosphere models. These models treat the star as a spherically symmetric body and assume hydrostatic equilibrium, radiative transfer, and local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE). Kurucz (1979) developed a comprehensive set of model atmospheres for various stellar types, which became a cornerstone for stellar spectroscopy. [1] Dimitri Mihalas (1978, 1984) made significant contributions to the development of computational methods for radiative transfer and the construction of model atmospheres. [2] [3] As computational power increased, researchers began to explore models that relax the assumption of LTE, leading to more accurate representations of stellar atmospheres, particularly for hot stars where departures from LTE are significant. The work by Ivan Hubeny and Thierry Lanz (1995) [4] on the TLUSTY code represents a significant advancement in the ability to model the spectra of hot stars with complex atomic species and line blanketing effects. The late 1990s and early 2000s saw the development of 3D hydrodynamic models of stellar atmospheres, which account for convective motions and provide a more realistic description of stellar surfaces as shown by Asplund et al. (2000) [5] and Nordlund et al. (2009). [6]

As computational methods improved, the focus shifted to applying stellar atmosphere models to large populations of stars. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in applying machine learning and data-driven approaches to the analysis of stellar spectra, driven by the wealth of data from large-scale surveys. The 21st century has seen a rapid expansion in the application of machine learning (ML) techniques in stellar spectroscopy, driven by the increasing availability of large datasets from astronomical surveys and advances in computational power. These ML techniques have been used for a wide range of applications, including the automated classification of stellar spectra, determination of stellar parameters, chemical abundance analysis, and the identification of unique stellar populations. The classification of stellar spectra, traditionally a manual and labour-intensive process, has been greatly enhanced by ML algorithms, particularly through the use of supervised and unsupervised learning methods. (Bailer-Jones et al. (2001), Fiorentin et al. (2007)). [7] [8]

ML techniques have been extensively used to estimate stellar parameters such as effective temperature, surface gravity, and metallicity from spectral data. In the early 2000s, Coryn A. L. Bailer-Jones and colleagues pioneered the use of artificial neural networks (ANNs) for the automated classification of stellar spectra and the determination of stellar parameters. (Bailer-Jones et al. (2000, 2001)). [7] Neves et al (2014) [9] developed a method of least square fitting of equivalent widths of the spectral lines in 530 – 690 nm range to predict effective temperatures and metallicities, and achieved an RMSE of 0.12 dex for metallicity and 293 K for temperature. Newton et al. (2015) [10] developed a calibration method for effective temperatures, radii, and bolometric luminosities using Mg and Al spectral features in low-resolution near-infrared spectra. Mann et al. (2015) [11] employed classical χ^2 minimization to match observed optical spectra to synthetic spectra from the CIFIST2011 library for calculating effective

temperatures. For metallicity, EWs of atomic lines in near-infrared spectra were used, based on calibrations from wide binaries. Cesetti et al. (2013) [12] proposed using sensitivity maps (derivatives of monochromatic fluxes with respect to atmospheric parameters) to rank spectral features. They searched for features that could predict effective temperature, surface gravity, and metallicity. Sarro et al (2018) [13] expands on previous studies by including a broader range of luminosity classes and training a genetic algorithm regression model on optimal spectral features, and using cross-validation to minimize overfitting. They have achieved an average uncertainty of greater 200 K on average, when predicting effective surface temperature and an uncertainty of 0.663 dex when predicting $\log g$ and that of 0.440 dex when predicting metallicity at 50 SNR.

Our work aims the determination of stellar parameters with more accuracy than previously accomplished by employing ever-increasing arsenal of powerful computing resources and robust machine learning techniques. We aim to create a neural network of medium density with a non-linear activation function predicting stellar properties such as effective temperature, metallicity and $\log G$ with uncertainty better than previous models, by using hydrogen Balmer lines and metallic lines in the visible range of 390– 550 nm for F Type stars, identified using the literature from a random population distribution of stars obtained from the XSHOOTER, ELODIE 3.0, MILES, and Indo-US stellar library, culminating to about 588 F Type stars. In this work we shall use pseudo-continuum normalisation of the observed stellar spectra, equivalent width calculation of the lines and model fitting of the spectral lines using SPECTRUM code of iSpec library. We employ a Bayesian regularization in the neural network, suitable for small and noisy dataset, and principal component analysis to determine the spectral features showing highest correlation with the stellar parameters. By knowing these we can also generate a correlation function showing how the spectral features in the stellar atmosphere of F type stars change throughout the population distribution, consisting dwarfs, subgiants and giants. We have chosen F Type stars because their closeness in properties with the G and K type stars which are like our Sun, known to support a habitable zone. In fact, F type stars are widely accepted to be the most luminous stars, capable of supporting life harbouring planets around them. So, a detailed spectroscopic study predicting their stellar properties such as metallicity, surface gravity and elemental abundance throughout their average lifetime of 2-4 billion years is a necessity to conduct further research on their habitability. Also, a peculiarity in the chemical composition of some pre main sequence stars in the spectral category of F class has long been reported, which can be studied in detail with the help of available spectroscopic survey. Our model can detect such stars with spectral class F, that are chemically peculiar owing to the surface chemical abundance, which can be analysed by our model by correlating the fundamental parameters of the stars with the line strengths of the spectral features.

The report is organised as follows: section 2 discusses briefly about the spectral libraries involved in the study. Section 3 discusses the methodology employed so far. Section 4 discusses briefly the results. Section 5 concludes the work done and discusses future road map.

2. Spectral Libraries

2.1 X-Shooter Stellar Library

The XSHOOTER Stellar Spectral Library (XSL) is an extensive and high-quality library of stellar spectra, created using the XSHOOTER spectrograph on the Very Large Telescope (VLT) at the European Southern Observatory (ESO) in Chile. The library covers a broad range of stellar types, including stars of various spectral classes, luminosity classes, and metallicities, providing a comprehensive dataset for stellar population synthesis, galactic archaeology, and stellar astrophysics. XSL is particularly distinguished by its wide wavelength coverage, spanning from the ultraviolet (UV) through the optical to the near-infrared (NIR) regions, roughly from 300 nm to 2.5 micrometres, all obtained simultaneously with high spectral resolution. This wide spectral range allows astronomers to analyse key diagnostic features across different parts of the stellar spectrum, enabling detailed studies of stellar atmospheres and the derivation of fundamental parameters such as effective temperature, surface gravity, and chemical abundances. The library's high resolution and quality, combined with the diversity of stellar types, make it an invaluable resource for modelling the integrated light of stellar populations, interpreting observations of distant galaxies, and refining theoretical models of stellar evolution. XSL has been widely used in various astrophysical research areas, including the study of star clusters, the calibration of other instruments, and the improvement of stellar models, making it a cornerstone for many modern astronomical studies. In this study, we have used 83 UV-Blue regions of F Type stars from the library. [14] [15]

Figure 1: Distribution of Stars in XSHOOTER Stellar Spectral Library

2.2 Indo-US Spectral Library

The Indo-US Library is a database of stellar spectra, encompassing more than 1000 stars, and covering the spectra region 3400–9500 angstrom at a resolution of ~ 1 Å FWHM. The primary emphasis of the spectral library is on broad wavelength coverage, particularly well into the blue, at resolution sufficient to resolve numerous diagnostic spectra features that can be used in the automated parameterization of spectra and in the population synthesis of galaxies. The INDO-US library spectra have been obtained with the no. 5 camera of the coude spectrograph and a Loral 3K \times 1K CCD using the 0.9 m coude feed

telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory. Two gratings have been used to provide spectral coverage from 3460 to 9464 Å, at a resolution of ~ 1 Å FWHM and at an original dispersion of 0.44 Å pixel⁻¹. For 885 stars we have complete spectra over the entire 3460 to 9464 Å wavelength region (neglecting small gaps of less than 50 Å), and partial spectral coverage for the remaining stars. The primary emphasis for the spectral database is obtaining stellar spectra covering a wide range in T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. We have used 202 F Type star spectra from the library for our purpose. [16]

Figure 2: Coude spectrograph at Kitt Peak National Observatory.

2.3 ELODIE 3.0

The ELODIE library is based on spectra retrieved from the Observatoire de Haute-Provence archive (Moultaka et al. 2004). The spectra were obtained with the ELODIE spectrograph attached to the 1.93m telescope, they have spectral resolution of about $R=42000$ and consists of 67 echelle orders covering in total the wavelength range 389.2 to 680 nm without any gap. The present version, ELODIE 3.1 is based on the same collection of spectra than ELODIE 3.0. The library includes 1959 spectra of 1388 stars obtained with the ELODIE spectrograph at the Observatoire de Haute-Provence 193cm telescope in the wavelength range 390 to 680 nm. It provides a wide coverage of atmospheric parameters: T_{eff} from 3100K to 50000K, $\log g$ from -0.25 to 4.9 and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ from -3 to +1. The library is given at two resolutions: R around 42000, with the flux normalized to the pseudo-continuum. A lower resolution version of the spectra (R around 10000), is calibrated in physical flux (reduced above earth atmosphere) with a broad-band photometric precision of 2.5% and narrow-band precision of 0.5%. The typical signal-to-noise ($S=N$) ratio per pixel at 550 nm is 150. We have included 229 F type star spectra for our analysis from this library. [17]

Figure 3: Distribution of ELODIE spectral library stars

2.4 MILES Library

The MILES library consists of 985 stars spanning a large range in atmospheric parameters (Sánchez-Blázquez et al. 2006a). The spectra were obtained at the 2.5 m Isaac Newton Telescope at the Observatorio del Roque de los Muchachos and cover the range 3525–7500Å with an originally estimated spectral resolution of 2.3 Å full-width half maximum (FWHM). A homogenized compilation of the stellar atmospheric parameters (Teff, Log(g), [Fe/H]) for the stars of this library was presented in Cenarro et al. (2007). We have incorporated 97 spectra F type star spectra from this library for our purpose. [18]

Figure 4: 2.5 Isaac Newton Telescope, where MILES spectra were obtained.

3. Methodology

3.1 Spectral Preprocessing

To begin analysis of the spectra, from the library, one must first ensure some preliminary preprocessing steps to be completed on the observed spectra. This is necessary to have all the observed spectra in the same format for analysis. The steps are specifically bringing the spectra from all of the spectral libraries into the identical spectral resolution, sampling, wavelength range and telluric velocity determination and telluric lines correction. The spectra from the libraries have been checked to be radial and telluric velocity corrected, already. We use a spectral analysis software [iSpec](#) to do the tasks (Blanco-Cuaresma et al (2014), Blanco-Cuaresma (2019)). [19] [20] The steps include :

- **Resolution Matching:** We match the resolution of all the spectra.
- **Resampling:** We resample all the different spectra from the libraries to a common wavelength step of 0.01 angstrom.
- **Continuum normalisation :** We fit a polynomial using iSpec spectral analysis software and perform normalisation.
- **Telluric Velocity Determination and Telluric line Correction.**
- **Line Fitting :** Line Mask identification, masking and fitting using SPECTRUM code.

The above four steps have been executed by our spectral preprocessing pipeline constructed using iSpec.

Figure 5 : Spectral pre-processing pipeline

3.2 Resolution matching

Resolution matching in astronomical spectra is a crucial process in the analysis and comparison of spectral data obtained from different instruments or observations under varying conditions. Astronomical spectra contain detailed information about the physical properties of celestial objects, such as their composition, temperature, velocity, and more. However, different spectrographs and telescopes have different resolving powers, leading to spectra with varying levels of detail (or

resolution). To accurately compare or combine spectra from different sources, it's essential to match their resolutions. We degrade the resolution of all the spectra to 2000, by Gaussian Kernel method using iSpec. For each flux value, the process will define a window based on the FWHM size which depends on the original and target resolution, build a gaussian using the sigma value and the wavelength values of the spectra window and finally convolve the spectra window with the gaussian and save the convolved value.

```
def degrade_resolution(spec):
    star_spectrum = ispec.read_spectrum(dir + spec)
    #-- Resolution degradation -----
    logging.info("Resolution degradation...")
    from_resolution = 10000
    to_resolution = 2000
    convolved_star_spectrum = ispec.convolve_spectrum(star_spectrum, to_resolution, \
                                                    from_resolution=from_resolution)
```


Figure 6 : Code for resolution matching (above), Resolution-degraded spectrum(bottom)

3.3 Resampling

One must homogenise the wavelength steps and match them for all the spectra from the different libraries. Data resampling by interpolation is a crucial technique in data analysis, particularly in the context of time series, signal processing, and spatial data analysis. It involves creating new data points within the range of an existing dataset, effectively increasing the resolution or filling in gaps in the data. Interpolation works by estimating the values at these new points based on the known values of the surrounding data. This method is widely used when working with datasets that are incomplete, have irregular intervals, or require finer granularity, like we have in the observed spectra, with inhomogeneous wavelength steps. We resample all the spectra by quadratic spline interpolation choosing wavelength step 0.01, between the wavelength range 390-550 nm using the iSpec because of their smoothing effect. Spline interpolation involves fitting a piecewise polynomial function, called a spline, through a set of data points. The polynomials are chosen not only to pass through the data points but also to ensure that the resulting curve is smooth at the joins between segments, meaning that the first and second derivatives of the curve are continuous across the entire data range.

```
def resample_spectrum(spec):
    star_spectrum = ispec.read_spectrum(dir + spec)
    #-- Resampling -----
    logging.info("Resampling...")
    wavelengths = np.arange(390.0, 550.0, 0.01)
    resampled_star_spectrum = ispec.resample_spectrum(star_spectrum, wavelengths, method="spline", zero_edges=True)
    resampled_star_spectrum = ispec.resample_spectrum(star_spectrum, wavelengths, method="bessel", zero_edges=True)
```

Figure 7: code for resampling

Figure 8: spectrum before resampling (left); after resampling (right)

3.4 Continuum normalisation

To determine the stellar parameters such as surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity, calculation of equivalent width of spectral features is required. For that, a continuum definition is required. Basically, the continuum of the radiation emitted from the photosphere of the stars are the radiation coming from the radiative zone, without getting reabsorbed by the interior layers. Ideally, the energy distribution of the radiation emitted by a star can be approximated by a blackbody radiation curve. The continuous spectrum can be thought of as coming from the hot surface of the star. Atoms in the atmosphere above the surface absorb certain characteristic wavelengths of this radiation, leaving dark “gaps” at the corresponding points in the spectrum, which are referred to as spectral features or spectral lines. In reality, however there is no such sharp separation between surface and atmosphere. All layers emit and absorb radiation, but the net result of these processes is that less energy is radiated at the wavelengths of the absorption lines. The accuracy of measurement of the equivalent width stands upon the most accurate determination of stellar continuum. However, in practice the continuum is difficult to define, especially because of multiplicity and overcrowding of spectral lines in high - resolution spectra, as well as intermixing of multiple spectral lines and line broadening.

Therefore, approximation of the continuum is necessary, when actual continuum is not known. For that purpose, pseudo-continuum has to be used. Pseudo-continuum is an approximated mathematical function, containing information for the construction of actual continuum, when original continuum is not exactly known. Adapted to the specific application they scale the intensity of the pseudo-continuum with the embedded absorptions proportionally to an appropriate new level. By the linear scaling the continuum-related measurement categories – peak absorption intensity P of a line profile and equivalent width EW – remain unchanged.

$$P_{absorption} = \frac{I_{abs,original}}{I_{cont,original}} = \frac{I_{abs,pseudo}}{I_{cont,pseudo}} \quad Eq. 1$$

Here, intensity of absorption line is I_{abs} and intensity of corresponding continuum is I_{cont} . Therefore, consequently, the equivalent widths of the lines calculated from original continuum and pseudo-continuum should be equivalent.

$$EQ_{pseudo} = EQ_{original} \quad Eq. 2$$

There are numerous ways, a pseudo-continuum can be defined. But for our work, we have chosen to fit a 4th order polynomial using ‘median+max’ technique in iSpec library, with median wavelength step of 0.01 nm and maximum wavelength selection of 1 nm. We have determined these values of the wavelength steps, as we have found they are optimum values for generating the continuum, without overlapping any of the spectral features.

To automatically detect and ignore strong absorption lines (for which the maximum filter is not enough), iSpec implements a probabilistic mechanism that can be controlled by setting a greater or lower probability threshold. This mechanism expects that the rate of change of the filtered fluxes should be similar (in chunks 20 times the max window size, with a minimum value of 10 nm), if a dramatic change is found then it is probable that is due to a strong absorption line and these points will be ignored. A higher probability threshold will accept less outlying rate changes and vice-versa.

With continuum obtained, we divide the continuum with the spectra and obtain the continuum normalized spectra.

```
def normalize_whole_spectrum_ignoring_prefixed_strong_lines(star_spectrum):
    """
    Use the whole spectrum but ignoring some strong lines, strategy 'median+max'
    """
    #star_spectrum = ispec.read_spectrum(dir + spec)

    #--- Continuum fit -----
    model = "Polynomy"
    degree = 4
    nknots = None # Automatic: 1 spline every 5 nm
    from_resolution = 2000

    # Strategy: Filter first median values and secondly MAXIMUMs in order to find the continuum
    order='median+max'
    median_wave_range=0.01
    max_wave_range=1.0

    strong_lines = ispec.read_line_regions("/home/iSpec/iSpec_v20230804/input/regions/strong_lines/absorption_lines.txt")
    star_continuum_model = ispec.fit_continuum(star_spectrum, from_resolution=from_resolution, \
        ignore=strong_lines, \
        nknots=nknots, degree=degree, \
        median_wave_range=median_wave_range, \
        max_wave_range=max_wave_range, \
        model=model, order=order, \
        automatic_strong_line_detection=True, \
        strong_line_probability=0.5, \
        use_errors_for_fitting=True)

    #--- Continuum normalization -----
    logging.info("Continuum normalization...")
    normalized_star_spectrum = ispec.normalize_spectrum(star_spectrum, star_continuum_model, consider_continuum_errors=False)
    # Use a fixed value because the spectrum is already normalized
    #star_continuum_model = ispec.fit_continuum(star_spectrum, fixed_value=1.0, model="Fixed value")
    logging.info("Saving spectrum...")
    return(normalized_star_spectrum)
```


Figure 9 : Code for continuum normalization (above), continuum normalized spectrum(bottom)

3.5 Telluric velocity determination

The strong and variable absorption of Earth’s atmosphere interferes with almost all ground-based astronomical observations. These gives rise to unwanted spectral absorption lines in an astronomical spectrum, which are called telluric lines. In the optical and infrared spectral range, the flux of a celestial body is diminished by extinction; in addition, so-called telluric absorption lines are imprinted on the spectra, a fact particularly relevant for high-resolution spectroscopy. iSpec includes an internal template, which corresponds to a synthetic spectrum of a star with Teff 5777.0, gravity (log g) 4.44 and metallicity 0.02 (solar type) which has been generated by using SPECTRUM, atomic data extracted

from the VALD database (350 to 11000 nm) and MARCS model atmospheres. These are used as template to identify and eliminate telluric lines. iSpec creates a mask from the given line list with a user defined size. If one or more mask lines fall into one range, the max depth is assigned as the mask value (otherwise it will be zero). Afterwards, it re-samples the mask uniformly in terms of velocity by using the specified velocity step (recommended to be half of the mask size). This implies that the distance between the elements in the mask is variable in wavelength but constant in velocity (depends on the mask size specified by the user). The following formula is used for determining the wavelength ranges:

$$\lambda_{i+1} = \lambda_i + \lambda_i \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{1-v/c}{1+v/c}}\right)$$

```
#-- Telluric velocity shift determination from spectrum -----
logging.info("Telluric velocity shift determination..")
# - Telluric
telluric_linelist_file = ispec_dir + "/input/linelists/CCF/Synth.Tellurics.500_1100nm/mask.lst"
telluric_linelist = ispec.read_telluric_linelist(telluric_linelist_file, minimum_depth=0.0)

models, ccf = ispec.cross_correlate_with_mask(star_spectrum, telluric_linelist, \
                                             lower_velocity_limit=-100, upper_velocity_limit=100, \
                                             velocity_step=0.5, mask_depth=0.01, \
                                             fourier = False, \
                                             only_one_peak = True)

vel_telluric = np.round(models[0].mu(), 2) # km/s
vel_telluric_err = np.round(models[0].emu(), 2) # km/s
```

Figure 10 : Code for telluric velocity determination.

3.6 Line Identification and fitting

For our analysis, we have chosen a common wavelength region of 390 -550 nm for all of the spectral libraries that have been incorporated in our model. We have used the spectral features of hydrogen Balmer series, Calcium and Magnesium lines, particularly show strong correlation in determining physical parameters, particularly surface temperature, surface gravity and metallicity, in this particular blue-ultra violet region of the spectrum for A-F classes of stars, as noted in several spectroscopic survey conducted such as MILES, LICK/IDS and LEGUE. [21] [18] [22]

Table 1: Spectral lines used to calculate equivalent width table, which has been used as input to our model.

element	wavelength peak	wavelength base	wavelength top	fwhm
CaK	393.34	392.31	394.18	0.9288
CaH	396.85	395.87	398.02	0.8614
Hd	410.16	408.87	411.6	0.6171
Ca I	422.64	422.1	423.05	0.3252
Hc	434.03	432.89	434.89	0.6562
Hb	486.12	485.09	486.89	0.5522
Mg	516.79	515.93	517.05	0.403

First, the common cross-matched atomic line profiles in the spectra were identified and selected by generating line masks of the corresponding line profiles from the VALD line list.

Next, for each defined line masks, a Gaussian was fitted according to given parameters using iSpec. It requires that the spectrum is corrected by its radial velocity and fitted continuum. The parameters of the Gaussian are set by iSpec, according to the resolution of the spectra.

Next, fitted lines was then cross-matched with an atomic line list VALD and if the difference between the theoretical and measured wavelength peak is smaller than a given limit, the atomic information will

be linked to line region. In case there is more than one line within the limit, the line with the greatest theoretical equivalent width (for solar atmospheric values) will be chosen.

Finally, iSpec will cross-match the lines with a telluric line list to mark with a * symbol if any line may be affected by telluric lines.

The Equivalent Widths of the fitted lines are then calculated using iSpec Program. The EW represents the strength of an absorption line, and it is defined as the width, in wavelength units, that a rectangular stripe of height I_c , in intensity units, would have if it had the same area as the actual line or—in other words—the wavelength interval that would be covered by a hypothetical, perfectly opaque absorption feature that removes the same amount of energy from the continuum flux.

Mathematically:

$$EQ = \sum_i \Delta\lambda_i \frac{I_c - I_i}{I_c} \quad Eq. 3$$

where $\Delta\lambda_i$ is the (constant) pixel size, I_c is the continuum level at the wavelength of the i th pixel, and I_i is the actual flux received by the i th pixel.

Figure 1: Equivalent Width

```
def fit_lines(star_spectrum, star_linemasks, star_continuum_model, telluric_linelist, vel_telluric):
    resolution = 2000
    smoothed_star_spectrum = ispec.convolve_spectrum(star_spectrum, resolution)
    linemasks = ispec.fit_lines(star_linemasks, star_spectrum, star_continuum_model, \
                               atomic_linelist = None, \
                               max_atomic_wave_diff = 0.005, \
                               #max_atomic_wave_diff = 0.00, \
                               telluric_linelist = telluric_linelist, \
                               smoothed_spectrum = smoothed_star_spectrum, \
                               check_derivatives = False, \
                               vel_telluric = vel_telluric, discard_gaussian=False, \
                               discard_voigt=True, \
                               free_mu=True, crossmatch_with_mu=False, closest_match=False)

    # Exclude lines that may be affected by tellurics
    rejected_by_telluric_line = (linemasks['telluric_wave_peak'] != 0)
    linemasks = linemasks[~rejected_by_telluric_line]

    # Exclude lines that have not been successfully cross matched with the atomic data
    # because we cannot calculate the chemical abundance (it will crash the corresponding routines)
    rejected_by_atomic_line_not_found = (linemasks['wave_nm'] == 0)
    linemasks = linemasks[~rejected_by_atomic_line_not_found]

    # Exclude lines with EW equal to zero
    rejected_by_zero_ew = (linemasks['ew'] == 0)
    linemasks = linemasks[~rejected_by_zero_ew]

    ew = linemasks['ew']
    ew_err = linemasks['ew_err']
    return (linemasks)
```

Figure 12: Code for fitting lines already cross-matched with VALD library, excluding telluric lines.

3.7 Neural Network Model

3.7.1 A brief introduction to neural networks

Neural networks are the class of machine learning algorithms proven to be one of the most potent approaches in data analysis by far. A simple machine learning model consists of the activation function, which takes the given training dataset as discrete inputs and outputs a predicted value. The expected value is fitted to actual training data, already provided by minimizing the difference between the expected value and the original value, minimizing the cost function over many iterations, and finally getting the function's parameters. Once the trained parameters of the activation function are obtained, it can predict the output with sufficient accuracy. A neural network consists of many layers of such activation functions, called 'neurons' or 'nodes,' where each neuron in each layer takes the output from every neuron from the previous layer and gives output to be taken as input for the neurons of the next layer. Anatomically, the very first layer of a neural network consists of the input features selected from the data set for the particular prediction required. The layers that follow, which calculate the weights of the model for prediction, are called hidden layers. The last layer, the output layer, predicts the required parameters based on the input parameters already fed as input using the trained weights. Each layer consists of the function parameters called 'weights,' which are found by the minimization of the cost function, just like in the case of a basic machine learning regression model, the only difference being the weights are computed sequentially for each of the layers meaning the weights of the final layer before the output layer is learned first, then using the values we learn the weights of the previous layer till we reach the first layer. This is known as backpropagation.

When the weights are computed, they are used by the activation function of the neurons of the very first hidden layer to output the predicted value, which is taken as input by the next hidden layer, which then outputs the predicted value to be taken as input by the next layer until the final output layer gives the final predicted value. This is called forward propagation.

Each iteration consists of such a back propagation and a forward propagation, by which the values of

Figure 2: Back-propagation learning

the weights are calculated with sufficient accuracy. For our purpose we input the equivalent width of the spectral features in the stellar spectra, obtained from the aforementioned libraries as input features, and stellar parameters of effective surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity logarithm as output features or targets/labels. The model can be trained to predict the given stellar parameters and finding correlation of the spectral features with the stellar parameters.

For accurately testing the efficiency and robustness of the model, the model trained on the input dataset needed to be tested. If the accuracy is low then the model is trained indefinitely until required or best possible accuracy is achieved. For that purpose, some amount of data is kept aside to do the test purpose and it is called test dataset. Further for training the model for best possible result, one need to keep changing the parameters of the model like number of regression nodes, layers, rate at which training is done etc called hyper-parameters. To tune the hyperparameter for optimum result one must use some

train data to measure the effectiveness of the parameters used in each iteration for validation. This is known as validation dataset.

However, any machine learning model not just neural networks suffers from a flaw called overfitting. Overfitting occurs when an algorithm fits too closely or even exactly to its training data, resulting in a model that can't make accurate predictions or conclusions from any data other than the training data. When machine learning algorithms are constructed, they leverage a sample dataset to train the model. However, when the model trains for too long on sample data or when the model is too complex, it can start to learn the “noise,” or irrelevant information, within the dataset. When the model memorizes the noise and fits too closely to the training set, the model becomes “overfitted,” and it is unable to generalize well to new data. If a model cannot generalize well to new data, then it will not be able to perform the classification or prediction tasks that it was intended for.

Another difficulty in training data models is underfitting. It is a scenario in data science where a data model is unable to capture the relationship between the input and output variables accurately, generating a high error rate on both the training set and unseen data. Underfitting occurs when a model is too simple, which can be a result of a model needing more training time, more input features, or less regularization.

The solution for overfitting is regularization. Regularization encompasses a range of techniques to correct for overfitting in machine learning models. Regularization provides this increased generalizability at the sake of increased training error. In other words, regularization methods typically lead to less accurate predictions on training data but more accurate predictions on test data. Basically, under the context of neural network, overfitting occurs when weights of the nodes keep increasing arbitrary in value after each iteration resulting in inaccurate results. To overcome this the weights are needed to be minimized without increasing indefinitely and converge to a particular value, predicting the optimum results. For that purpose, a term involving weights is added to the cost function, with a parameter known as lambda or regularization constant.

Figure 3: Overfitting and Underfitting illustrated

We shall discuss here only such method, which we have used in our model and that is the Bayesian regularization method in the next section.

3.5.2 Our Bayesian Regularized Neural Network Model

The objective of our training process will be to minimize the sum of squared errors: $E_D = \sum (t - a)^2$ where t is the target(stellar parameters of temperature, metallicity and $\log g$) and a is the neural network's prediction. Typically, training aims to reduce the sum of squared errors $F = E_D$. However, regularization adds an additional term; the objective function becomes $F = \beta E_D + \alpha E_W$, where E_W is the sum of squares of the network weights, and α and β are objective function parameters. The relative size of the objective function parameters dictates the emphasis for training. If $\alpha \ll \beta$, then the training algorithm will drive the errors smaller. If $\alpha \gg \beta$, training will emphasize weight size reduction at the expense of network errors, thus producing a smoother network response. In the Bayesian framework the weights of the network are considered random variables. After the data is taken, the density function

for the weights can be updated according to Bayes' rule: $P(D|W, \beta, M) = \exp(-\beta E_D)$, where D represents the data set, M is the particular neural network model used, and w is the vector of network weights. If we assume that the noise in the training set data is Gaussian and that the prior distribution for the weights is Gaussian, the probability densities can be written as

$$P(D|W, \beta, M) = \frac{\exp(-(\beta E_D + \alpha E_W))}{Z_D(\beta)} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Here, $Z_D(\beta)$ is the normalization factor. In this Bayesian framework, the optimal weights should maximize the posterior probability $P(D|W, \beta, M)$. Maximizing the posterior probability is equivalent to minimizing the regularized objective function $\beta E_D + \alpha E_W$. This is known as the Bayesian Regularization. [23] [24]

We input the calculated equivalent widths of the 7 Balmer series, Calcium and Magnesium lines listed in Table 1 for all the 588 stars from the spectral libraries to our neural network and use the 3 physical parameters consisting of surface temperature, metallicity and surface gravity logarithm as the target or labels. We have split the dataset into train and test sets in the 80-20 ratio. We have generated three models, each for the surface temperature, surface gravity and metallicity, using torchbnn, a Bayesian Neural Network package, based on pytorch. The three models are:

- Surface Temperature Model:
 - Architecture: Sequential(Input Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.01, prior sigma=0.01, input features=7), ReLU layer, Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.01, prior sigma=0.01, neurons=15), ReLU layer, Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.01, prior sigma=0.01, neurons=5, output feature=surface temperature)
 - Optimizer: Adam Optimizer (learning rate=0.01, regularization =0.0001, steps=10000)
- Surface Gravity Model:
 - Architecture: Sequential(Input Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.00001, prior sigma=0.00001, input features=7), ReLU layer, Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.00001, prior sigma=0.00001, neurons=20), ReLU layer, Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.01, prior sigma=0.00001, neurons=10, output feature=surface gravity logarithm)
 - Optimizer: Adam Optimizer (learning rate=0.01, regularization =0.0001, steps =500)
- Metallicity Model:
 - Architecture: Sequential(Input Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.0001, prior sigma=0.0001, input features=7), ReLU layer, Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.0001, prior sigma=0.0001, neurons=15), ReLU layer, Bayesian Linear layer (prior mu=0.01, prior sigma=0.0001, neurons=10, output feature=surface gravity logarithm)
 - Optimizer: Adam Optimizer (learning rate=0.01, regularization =0.0001, steps = 500)

4. Results

Our surface temperature model is predicting effective temperature within error margin of close to 200 Kelvin RMSE. Our metallicity model is giving prediction within error margin of 0.5 dex and the surface gravity model providing results within the error margin of 0.5 dex, which are close to the error margins we were aiming for. Our results show the Bayesian regularized NN model gives much better result within a small stellar population taken for study, than many other NN models, applied to the same

population, using usual regularization. The test error for the surface temperature model reach convergence to a RMSE value close to 200 after 10000 iterations. The test error for the metallicity model and surface gravity converge to a RMSE value close to 0.5 dex after 500 iterations. The temperature model takes more steps to converge by virtue of the fact that the parameter space of the temperature covers a broader range from around 4000 Kelvin-8000 Kelvin, but that of the surface gravity and metallicity ranges from $\text{Log } G \sim 2.5-4.75$ and $\text{Fe}/\text{H} \sim -2 - +1$. Also, noticeable, that the stars for which the model fails to predict less accurately is because those stars are more metal-rich than usual stars, with similar surface temperature and metallicity. Our model can be extended further in future in identifying such composition anomaly in the stellar surface. [25]

Figure 4: Surface Gravity Model Prediction and Gradient Descent

Figure 5: Metallicity Model Prediction and Gradient Descent

Figure 6: Effective Surface Temperature Model Prediction and Gradient Descent

5. Conclusion

Although we have obtained a model which can predict over small populations of stars with comparatively more accuracy than previous models, we can do better. The RMSE of the predictions of our Bayesian NN model can be further decreased by the following procedures:

- A combined dataset composed of the PHOENIX synthetic spectra, of corresponding physical parameters in the range of that of the observed stellar spectra of F Type stars in the Xshooter stellar spectral library can be created for input dataset to our model. This will help interpolate the equivalent widths of the spectral features and further refine our model greatly improving our prediction accuracy.
- A hyperparameter tuned Bayesian Neural Network Model can give us even better result. Hyperparameters are model parameters such learning rate, number of neurons in each layer, regularization parameters alpha and beta etc.
- After the completion of the building of the optimum model we can predict over the physical parameter of the F-type stars to build a correlation function of equivalent widths of the spectral features predicting the physical parameters.
- A principal component analysis can be run to predict which lines are most typical in predicting the physical parameters.
- We also intend to increase the size of our dataset by including LAMOST low resolution spectra, which has more than 10 million spectra, of about 9 million stellar spectra. (Liu et al 2020) For the preliminary model, we plan to include almost 2000 F type stars out of a million from the LAMOST survey Data Release 10, which will be particularly helpful for our model to predict the metallicity of the F stars in the Milky way, more accurately, as the survey have studied metallicity distribution and chemical abundance in our galaxy extensively.

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